

Experts Speak

THE NUANCES OF MEDIA TROLLING

Concept Note

Online disinformation, spread of deceptive messages, and making unsolicited and/or controversial comments with the intent to provoke an emotional, knee-jerk reaction to engage in arguments are pernicious. This has become a global phenomenon. Not only sadist individuals resort to such acts, the political machinery in many countries makes use of ‘trolling’ and ‘fake news’ dissemination to manufacture public consent or dissent on issues to further their parochial interests. Adrian Shahbaz, a Freedom House research manager, opines that “the unprecedented rise of state-sponsored manipulation and election meddling online was unique to 2017, and may prove much harder to fix than other ills”, implying gradual institutionalization and political patronage of such tactics.

More importantly, the socio-political impact of such a process is alarming. Internet trolling is damaging people, public issues, values of organizations, national economy, social fabric, etc. in numerous ways. The intentional insults and threats inflicted in an organized way make it hard for the targeted person or organization. Sometimes attacks have real-world consequences, as when trolls get hold of the target’s personal information. India has seen in the recent past spread of fake news on child kidnapping, cow slaughter, etc. A few months ago the Indian Foreign Minister Sushma Swaraj has been the subject of offensive tweet-trolling, following a passport row involving an interfaith couple. This comes after several years of sinister trolling of many opposition political activists, and women journalists.

It is surprising that social media platforms do little, if anything, to stop the trolling phenomenon. For certain sections find trolling and ‘fake news’ dissemination useful, the menace is here to stay and likely to get murkier. As noted by Oxford University Press, “Anyone with a laptop and an Internet connection can be in the news business”. With so-called ‘citizen journalists’ on the rise and coming up of an attractive business model for spreading lies, is the world moving towards the dark age of journalism?

Liberal Studies journal invites three eminent scholars/experts to ponder over the issue of ‘trolling’ and ‘fake news’ and their implications. **Pradeep Mallik**, with his vast experience in the mainstream Indian media, argues that internet does not create special threats. It is the people in the public sphere who blurt things offensive. The approach should be to not throw the baby with bathwater. **Kriti Singh**, having background in media and communication, opines that the menace of trolls seems to be here to stay, but the answer is to not take the bait, and, rather choose discourses and online acquaintances wisely, self-monitor the social media networks and digital conversations, using strong privacy settings, and ultimately using the very technology being misused. **Binita Parikh** explains that fake news emerges not in vacuum; rather there are creators of ‘fake news’. There are now people and organisations that exploit the gullibility of unsuspecting audiences by ‘fake news’. Concern over this problem is now becoming universal with global proportions and ramifications. A new system of safeguards has now become necessary to combat this evil.